
Effect of Social Media Marketing on the Financial Performance of Small and Medium Sized Enterprises (SMES) In Mezam Division (North West Region), Cameroon

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Abstract: This study examines the effect of social media marketing on the financial performance of small and medium size enterprises in mezam division (NWR) Cameroon. The study has as main objective to examine the effect of social media marketing on the financial performance of small and medium sized enterprises in mezam division (NWR), Cameroon. Primary data were collected through semi structured questionnaire from sampled respondents in the SMEs sector incorporating social media marketing in their business with the use of a purposive sampling technique. The data was entered into the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) and analyzed using descriptive, regression and correlation analyses. Ordinary least squares technique was deployed in doing regression analysis. The results of the analysis show that adoptions of social media marketing tools such as facebook, youtube, instagram and other controled variables significantly affect the financial performance of SMEs. However, the result suggests that for SMEs to sustain and improve their financial performance on social media marketing, there is need to take advantage of more than one of the social media marketing tools as part of marketing strategies and as well small and medium size enterprises should deliver some value-added services, like online shopping, booking or electronic billing and lead to the direction of ecommerce in view of growth, sustainability and expansion.

Key words: Social Media Marketing, Financial performance, Small and Medium Spze Enterprise.

INTRODUCTION

In the highly competitive business environment and unstable economic situation, many small businesses face new challenges, including the increasing variation and uncertainty in market demand and strong competition brought about by the globalisation process. On one hand, Small and Medium Size Enterprises (SMEs) have limitations in terms of finance, human resources, and organisational resources, which make the company very vulnerable in the market. On the other hand, there are ways that can be used to improve SMEs in terms of expanding networks in new markets to overcome company limitations, pursue access to external resources, and to develop product innovations. This capacity seems to be supported by the adoption of information and communication technology, which affect sales performance (Bocconcelli, *et al.*, 2017).

Social media is changing the traditional methods of presence. The traditional techniques of marketing using print and electronic media along with internet marketing and lead generation were used to drive traffic to a business and its website. As search engine algorithms evolve, website owners have to stay on their toes to make sure their website is constantly updated with relevant and current information to prevent being devalued in search results. Today, social media like, Facebook pages, Twitter accounts, and YouTube channels are being seen as sites in their own right to mark the presence. Social media allows businesses to crowd source Ideas. Before businesses launch a new product or service, they would like to have some ideas about what people

think about it. So by engaging with prospects and customers via social media, one can actually ask the fans and followers what colors they prefer or what types of features they want. Thus SMEs can involve consumers in valuable free market research, by asking their opinions and can help establish credibility by showing that their opinions matter. After seeing their ideas becoming a reality, business has more than likely just increased their customer base. Customers increasingly make purchasing decisions based on businesses' social media presence (Hajli, 2014; Hutter *et al.*, 2013).

Businesses are changing marketing strategies based on information they find in social media feeds from their competitors. By keeping an eye on competitors, their strengths and weaknesses can determine their marketing efforts. This gathered information helps to implement things that might be needed to improve such as social media campaigns, contests, giveaways or types of content the followers may be responding to the most. Social Media allows business to be more transparent. The process of taking a prospect to the point of becoming a customer has slowed down somewhat due to consumers' awareness. People want to buy from those companies who have established credibility and who seem to be totally transparent in their advertising campaigns. Social media is changing people's opinions of businesses. By providing messages that are open, transparent and helpful, social audiences will learn that your business cares about its customers and potential customers. One can position their company as a valuable resource by simply sharing information like advice, tips, or just answering questions about the industry. Without social media marketing strategies, small businesses may lose customers if they are unable to compete with the marketing approaches larger firms use (Clark & Calli, 2015; Taneja & Toombs, 2014).

Background

Blackshaw & Nazzaro, (2004) define social media or consumer-generated media as "a variety of new sources of online information that are created, initiated, circulated and used by consumer's intent on educating each other about products, brands, services, personalities, and issues". Filo *et al.* (2015) viewed social media as "new media technologies facilitating interactivity and co-creation that allow for the development and sharing of user-generated content among and between organisations (teams, government agencies and media groups) and individuals (customers, athletes and journalists).

In general, social media is a collection of online platforms and tools that people use to share content, profiles, opinions, insights, experiences, perspectives and media itself, facilitating conversations and interactions online between groups of people. Social Media is the platform/tools. Social Networking is the act of connecting on social media platforms. Social Media Marketing is how businesses join the conversation in an authentic and transparent way to build relationships.

According to SisiraNeti, (2011), social media, today, is among the 'best opportunities available' to a brand for connecting with prospective consumers. Social media is the medium to socialize. These new media win the trust of consumers by connecting with them at a deeper level. Social media marketing is the new mantra for several brands since early last year. Marketers are taking note of many different social media opportunities and beginning to implement new social initiatives at a higher rate than ever before. Social media marketing and the businesses that utilize it have become more sophisticated. One cannot afford to have no presence on the social channels if the competitor is making waves with its products and services. The explosion of social media phenomenon is as mind boggling as that and the pace at which it is growing is maddening.

Small and Medium Sized Enterprises (SMEs)

In Cameroon, small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) are regarded as vectors for job and wealth creation. According to statistics from the Ministry of Small and Medium-Sized Enterprises, Social Economy, and Handicrafts, there are more than 400,000 active companies in the informal sector. Ninety-nine percent (99%) of these companies are SMEs, whose active presence helps generate growth and redistribute wealth in society. The important role played by SMEs in

reducing poverty in Cameroon is gaining recognition. SMEs contribute around 36% of Cameroon's GDP, make-up over 90% of businesses in Cameroon, and employ above 60% of the population. That notwithstanding, evident realities indicate that enormous potentials inherent in this sector are unfortunately not fully harnessed – especially given that more than 70% of SMEs still operate informally

Financial Performance

Related literature classified performance standards into financial and non-financial. Financial performance standards include return on investment, earnings per share, revenue growth, and profit merging. Non-financial performance standards include satisfying customers' and Employees' needs, production efficiency, and quality of services provided. Performance standards are seen as critical decision-making process for organization. These standards help the organization achieve its objectives in a logical and effective way, and they should support performance indicators and they support the external and internal organization environment. Nevertheless, the difficulty lies in that many firms still have old standards that are not harmonious with their goals. Therefore, firms should adapt to changes in market environment and be aware of the completion of its objectives.

McLuhan's Media Theory

McLuhan is a Canadian philosopher and educator, the author of the famous quote "the media is the message" (McLuhan 1995). He argued that the media itself, rather the actual content of the media, will transform people and society. The actual messages people are communicating won't be any different on the new media; the interactivity and frequency of new communication pattern will change our behavior forever. Thus, the media's effects on society are much greater than the content of the media. He separates media into "cool" media and "hot" media. The former one requires a viewer to exert much effort and participation in understanding the content, such as television, seminars, or cartoons; the latter refers to those media that enhance one sense, so the viewers do not need to exert much effort, such as films, radio, and photography (McLuhan 1995).

If we use McLuhan's arguments, social media will transform the users not due to the content it contains, but due to the mode of communication it entails. For example, Twitter is only a micro-blogging service with a limitation of 140 characters. Theoretically one can perform all the functions of Twitter through a blog service. However, it is exactly its limiting factor which made Twitter more nimble and real-time. Many breaking news stories were spread out on Twitter, such as China's Sichuan earthquake and Mumbai's terrorist attack in 2008 (Parr 2009). As business managers and consumers, one needs to realize the changing behavior due to the usage of new social media services and adopt an attitude of acceptance toward those technologies and behavior.

Marketing equity theory

Developed by kim & kom (2012), this theory state that social media marketing have proved to have a positive effect on the performance of an organization. The authors of the theory initially focused on the marketing activities used by luxury fashion brands to market their products. They included entertainment in the particular sector of the industry, customer interaction based on the goal of the business, trend, customization of the product and services offered to the target population for consumption and word of mouth. Their impact on firm performance was analysed in terms of brand equity, customer equity, purchase intention, value equity and equity linkage. Kim and kum (2012) concluded that this model provide a solid view on the working of social media marketing

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The research design adopted for the study was a survey design and the approach employed was the quantitative approach. The survey design was chosen because it provides a quantitative description of trends, attitudes, or opinions of a population by studying the sample of that population (Fowler,

2002). The study sought to establish the relationships between the effectiveness of social media marketing in small business performance. Descriptive design was convenient for this study as it enabled the researcher make inferences on the role of social media marketing to small businesses. The study was also cross-sectional in the sense that it represented a snapshot of one point in time. The quantitative approach was adopted so as to be able to describe and explain relationships between variables.

AREA OF STUDY

Geographical Scope

This study was carried out in Mezam Division located in the North West Region of Cameroon. The division is made up of rural, semi-urban and urban areas. The rural settlements are sparsely populated and where the local inhabitants are mostly involved in subsistence and plantation agriculture. Meanwhile, in the semi-urban and urban areas, the local population is involved in agriculture, manufacturing and other tertiary activities. The geographical scope of this study was small businesses in Mezam. Thus, other business out of Mezam will not be included in the study. With current rate of unemployment in Cameroon many individual have resorted to carrying out small scale businesses for sustainability. In the North West region in particular, it is common to find small scale business such as fashion clothing, hair dressing saloons, tailoring workshops and a host of others.

TARGET POPULATION, SAMPLE AND SAMPLING TECHNIQUE

Target Population

The study population is all the SMEs operating within Mezam and the target population was all businesses listed by the divisional tax centers in Mezam. The study population consists of all SMEs in mezam division incorporating social media marketing in their business, where the number of employees in each business is ranging from 1-30 employees. Target population is defined as the entire aggregation of respondents that meet the designated set of criteria (Kothari, 2004). It is a set of all members of a real or hypothetical set of people, events or subjects to which a researcher wishes to generalize his/her results (Ngechu, 2004).

Sample size

The sample size for the study is 304 and, this was estimated from the 2690 small and medium size enterprises in mezam division. The formula stated below was used in calculating the sample size of the study.

$$\frac{NZ^2P(1 - P)}{d^2(N - 1) + Z^2P(1 - P)}$$

Source: (Amin, 2005)

Where:

N=Total number of participants

Z= Z value corresponding to the confidence level, =95%

d= absolute precision =5% (It should be noted that the smaller the precision, the higher the sample size and the more reliable the findings). A precision value of 5% was them considered acceptable for a good statistical significance.

P=expected proportion in the population =50% for optimal sample size estimation.

$$\frac{2690 * 1.96^2 * 50(1 - 50)}{0.5^2(2690 - 1) + 1.96^2 * 50(1 - 50)}$$

$$\frac{2690*3.8416*2450}{25(2989)+3.4816*2450}$$

$$\begin{array}{r} 27998064.8 \\ \hline 74725+8529.92 \\ \hline 27998064.8 \\ \hline 83254.92 \end{array}$$

S =336

Sampling Technique

After determining the number of respondents, purposive sampling will be applied to select respondents from each business. Only businesses that are register under the tax department will be considered for the study. Participant consideration was confirmed to fit the following considerations under gender (male and female), age (>20 years), education level (from college level and above), longevity of service (>0 years) and position of employment. The unit of analysis was the directors and employees in each of the selected business.

Nature and Source of data

3.4.1. Nature of Data

Primary data were used for this study to capture the various specific objectives. Primary sources comprising of staff of the various businesses that will be surveyed. To facilitate the collection of data, questionnaires were used.

Instrument of Data Collection

Semi structured questionnaires were used to collect data. According to Davies & Dodd (2002), the questionnaire is common instrument for observing data beyond the physical reach of the observer. The questionnaire included closed ended questions where responses are restricted to small set of responses that generate precise answers to develop the empirical study. The closed ended questions will be used for easy coding and analysis. This was in line with Creswell and Mille (2000), who argued that in a questionnaire there may be open and closed questions. This approached was considered to be best suited for this study considering the peculiarity of social media marketing. It was necessary to guide a predetermine guide for easy comprehension of the subject matter

Technique of Data Analysis

Analysis of data was done in order to answer the research question of this study. To facilitate the data analysis process as a result of the multivariate nature of the research, multiple correspondence analysis was used to detect and represent underlying structures in a data set.

The data was entered into the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) and analyzed using descriptive, regression and correlation analyses. Ordinary least squares technique was deployed in doing regression analysis. The linear regression enabled the researcher to understand the mean change in the dependent variable given a one-unit change in each independent variable. Correlation analysis was done to measures the strength of association between the two variables and the direction of the relationship. In doing the analysis, descriptive statistics was employed to characterize the data based on its properties. The results were presented on frequency distribution tables and bar charts. Here the interest was focused on frequency of occurrence across attributes of measures.

FINDINGS

Question one: Does the use of Facebook affect the financial performance of small and medium size enterprises in Mezam Division NWR, Cameroon?

Table 12: Respondents opinion on the use of Facebook

Opinion Statements	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
Facebook has enable increase in brand awareness of your products and services.	137 (44.6%)	130 (42.3%)	24 (7.8%)	0 (0.0%)	16 (5.2%)
Facebook helps customer identify with SME's product brand.	98 (31.9%)	161 (52.4%)	32 (10.4%)	16 (5.2%)	0 (0.0%)
Promotions and discounts displayed on the business Facebook page increases sales.	120 (39.1%)	105 (34.2%)	66 (21.5%)	8 (2.6%)	8 (2.6%)
Facebook facilitates interaction and collaboration between customers and the business.	160 (52.1%)	106 (34.5%)	25 (8.1%)	16 (5.2%)	0 (0.0%)
Facebook has become a major source of interactive platform with your clients.	98 (31.9%)	145 (47.2%)	24 (7.8%)	24 (7.8%)	16 (5.2%)
I use Facebook to understand customer needs.	56 (18.2%)	112 (36.5%)	82 (26.7%)	32 (10.4%)	25 (8.1%)
I rely on Facebook to reach new customers.	80 (26.1%)	106 (34.5%)	25 (8.1%)	48 (15.6%)	48 (15.6%)
Multiple response set (MRS)	749 (34.9%)	865 (40.3%)	278 (12.9%)	144 (6.7%)	113 (5.3%)

Source : Author (2021)

As shown on table above, all the 307 respondents do use Facebook as a marketing strategy to their business and, cumulatively, findings showed that a majority of the respondents 267 (86.9%) accepted that Facebook has increased awareness of their business brand. Cumulatively, findings also showed that a majority of the respondents 259 (84.3%) accepted that Facebook has enable their customers to know their business brand. Cumulatively, findings also showed that a majority of the respondents 225 (73.3%) accepted that promotion and discount display on Facebook has increased their sales.

Furthermore, cumulatively, findings also showed that a majority of the respondents 266 (86.6%) accepted that Facebook has facilitated interaction and collaboration between customers and their business. Also, cumulatively, findings showed that a majority of the respondents 243 (79.1%) accepted that Facebook has become a major source of interactive platform with their clients. Cumulatively, findings also showed that 168 (54.7%) of the respondents accepted that they use Facebook to understand their customers' needs. Finally, cumulatively, findings showed that a majority of the respondents 186 (60.6%) accepted that they rely on Facebook to reach new customers. In overall, cumulatively findings showed that a majority of the respondents 75.2 accepted that the use of Facebook as a marketing strategy has been of benefit to their business while 12.0% of them denied and 12.9% of them are uncertain.

Question two: What is the effect of YouTube on the financial performance of small and size enterprises in Mezam Division (NWR), Cameroon?

Table 13 : Respondents opinion on the use of YouTube

Opinion Statements	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
The clarity of your products through Youtube has increase the consumer purchasing decision in your business.	34 (14.0%)	73 (30.0%)	72 (29.6%)	40 (16.5%)	24 (9.9%)
Using Youtube in business has cut down the cost of operation.	0 (0.0%)	97 (39.9%)	40 (16.5%)	82 (33.7%)	24 (9.9%)
When starting using Youtube in marketing your business, you have been increasing the number of sales.	8 (3.3%)	80 (32.9%)	83 (34.2%)	32 (13.2%)	40 (16.5%)
Using Youtube to market your business is inconvenient especially with the environment you live in.	66 (27.2%)	33 (13.6%)	32 (13.2%)	88 (36.2%)	24 (9.9%)
I find it easy to reach a wider population on Youtube compared to the traditional advertising way.	49 (20.2%)	41 (16.9%)	65 (26.7%)	56 (23.0%)	32 (10.4%)
Multiple response set (MRS)	157 (12.9%)	324 (26.7%)	292 (24.0%)	298 (24.5%)	144 (11.9%)

n=243

Among the 243 respondents that accepted to use YouTube as a marketing strategy, cumulatively, findings showed that 107 (44.0%) of them accepted that the clarity of their products through YouTube has increase consumers' purchasing decision. Cumulatively, findings showed also that 97 (39.9%) of the respondents accepted that YouTube has cut down the cost of their business operation. Also, cumulatively, findings showed that 88 (36.2%) of the respondents accepted that YouTube usage has increased their sales.

Finally, cumulatively, findings also showed that 90 (37.1%) of the respondents accepted that YouTube has made it easier for them to reach a wider population when compared to the traditional way of advertising. In overall, cumulatively findings showed that 39.6% of the respondents accepted that the use of YouTube as a marketing strategy has been of benefit to their business while 36.4% of them denied and 24.0% of them being neutral.

Question Three: How does Instagram affect the financial performance of small and medium size enterprises in Mezam Division (NWR), Cameroon?

Table 14: Respondents opinion on the use of Instagram

Opinion Statements	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
Instagram has enabled your business to engage easily with customers by sending samples, adverts.	41 (18.7%)	64 (29.2%)	50 (22.8%)	48 (21.9%)	16 (7.3%)
Instagram has influence buying decision in customers and increase more selling.	40 (18.3%)	81 (37.0%)	41 (18.7%)	25 (11.4%)	32 (14.6%)
Use of Instagram has pushed your business towards E-commerce use in conducting business such as internet advertisements.	40 (18.3%)	81 (37.0%)	42 (19.2%)	40 (18.3%)	16 (7.3%)

It is easy to connect with your customers through Instagram when passing marketing information.	41 (18.7%)	57 (26.0%)	56 (25.6%)	41 (18.7%)	24 (11.0%)
Instagram enables SMEs to reach a wider range of youths relating to their products at lesser cost.	50 (22.8%)	65 (29.7%)	24 (11.0%)	32 (14.6%)	48 (21.9%)
Instagram led to more creativity in advertising and personal selling when meeting customer's needs.	48 (21.9%)	24 (11.0%)	66 (30.1%)	41 (18.7%)	40 (18.3%)
I personally engage current and potential customers on Instagram.	40 (18.3%)	66 (30.1%)	32 (14.6%)	48 (21.9%)	33 (15.1%)
Multiple response set (MRS)	300 (19.6%)	438 (28.6%)	311 (20.3%)	275 (17.9%)	209 (13.6%)

n=219

Among the 219 respondents that accepted to use Instagram as a marketing strategy, cumulatively, findings showed that 105 (47.9%) of them accepted that Instagram has enabled them to engage easily with customers by sending samples, adverts. Cumulatively, findings also showed that 121 (55.3%) of the respondents accepted that Instagram has influence the buying decision of their customers and increase their sales.

Cumulatively, findings also showed that another 121 (55.3%) of the respondents accepted that the use of Instagram has pushed their business towards E-commerce use. To elucidate, cumulatively, findings also showed that 98 (44.7%) of the respondents accepted that they easily connect with customers through Instagram when passing marketing information. Also, cumulatively, findings showed that 115 (52.5%) of the respondents accepted that Instagram enabled them to reach a wider range of youths relating to their products at lesser cost.

Cumulatively, findings also showed that 72 (32.9%) of the respondents accepted that Instagram has led to more creativity in advertising and personal selling when meeting customer's needs. Finally, cumulatively, findings also showed that 106 (48.4%) of the respondents accepted that they engage current and potential customers on Instagram.

In overall, cumulatively, findings showed that 48.2% of the respondents accepted that the use of Instagram have been of benefit to them to their business while 31.5% of them disagreed and 20.3% of them being neutral.

Hypotheses Results

Testing of hypothesis one (Ho1): There is no significant effect of the use of Facebook on the financial performance of small and medium size enterprises in Mezam Division (NWR), Cameroon.

Table 16: The effect of the use of Facebook on the financial performance of small and medium size enterprises

		Use of Facebook	Financial performance of SMEs
Pearson test	R-value	1	.494**
	P-value		.000
	N	307	307

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source : Author (2021)

Statistically, findings showed that the use of Facebook has a very significant, positive and relatively strong effect on the financial performance of SMEs ($P < 0.001$, $r < 0.05$). The positive sign of the correlation coefficient value ($R = 0.494^{**}$) implies that the financial performance of SMEs is more likely to increase when owners of SMEs adequately use Facebook as a marketing strategy of their products. Therefore, the hypothesis that states that there is no significant effect of the use of Facebook on the financial performance of small and medium size enterprises in Mezam Division (NWR), Cameroon was rejected.

Testing of hypothesis two (Ho2): There is no significant effect of YouTube on the financial performance of small and medium size enterprises in Mezam Division (NWR), Cameroon.

Table 17: The effect of the use of YouTube on the financial performance of small and medium size enterprises

		Use of YouTube	Financial performance of SMEs
Pearson test	R-value	1	.576**
	P-value		.000
	N	307	307

****.** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source : Author (2021)

Statistically, findings showed that the use of YouTube has a very significant, positive and strong effect on the financial performance of SMEs ($P < 0.001$, $r < 0.05$). The positive sign of the correlation coefficient value ($R = 0.576^{**}$) implies that the financial performance of SMEs is more likely to increase when owners of SMEs adequately use YouTube as a marketing strategy of their products. Therefore, the hypothesis that states that there is no significant effect of YouTube on the financial performance of small and medium size enterprises in Mezam Division (NWR), Cameroon was rejected.

Testing of hypothesis three (Ho3): There is no significant effect of Instagram on the financial performance of small and medium size enterprises in Mezam Division (NWR), Cameroon.

Table 18: The effect of the use of Instagram on the financial performance of small and medium size enterprises

		Use of Instagram	Financial performance of SMEs
Pearson test	R-value	1	.204**
	P-value		.000
	N	307	307

****.** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source : Author (2021)

Statistically, findings showed that the use of Instagram has a very significant, positive and moderate effect on the financial performance of SMEs ($P < 0.001$, $r < 0.05$). The positive sign of the correlation coefficient value ($R = 0.204^{**}$) implies that the financial performance of SMEs is more likely to increase when owners of SMEs adequately use Instagram as a marketing strategy of their products. Therefore, the hypothesis that states that there is no significant effect of Instagram on the financial performance of small and medium size enterprises in Mezam Division (NWR), Cameroon was rejected.

The regression analysis between social media marketing and financial performance of SMEs

Variables	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	P-value
	B	Linearised Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	-.757	1.120		-.676	.500

Use of Facebook	.418	.051	.405	8.204	.000
Use of Instagram	.103	.035	.143	2.953	.004
Use of YouTube	.605	.061	.498	9.995	.000
Model Summary					
R	.736 ^a				
R-squared	.542				
Adjusted R squared	.535				
Std. Error of the Estimate	2.89360				
ANOVA Statistics					
F test	78.477				
Prob > F	.000 ^b				

a. Dependent variable: Financial performance of SMEs

b. Predictors: (Constant), Use of YouTube, Use of Instagram, Use of Facebook

Source : Author (2021)

Findings from the regression analysis showed social media marketing have a very significant, positive and strong effect on the financial performance of SMEs. Social media marketing was tested to affect the financial performance of SMEs by 54.2% (R-squared =0.542). The variability explained by the model was very significant (F=78.477, P<0.001, far<0.05) and the overall variability explained was 73.6% (R= 0.736), with 26.7% of the variability not explained.

Discussion of Results and Conclusion

In line with hypothesis one of this study which states that there is no significant effect of the use of facebook on the financial performance of small and medium sized enterprises in mezam division (NWR) Cameroon. Statistically, findings showed that the use of Facebook has a very significant, positive and relatively strong effect on the financial performance of SMEs (P < 0.001, far < 0.05). The positive sign of the correlation coefficient value (R= 0.494^{**}) implies that the financial performance of SMEs is more likely to increase when owners of SMEs adequately use Facebook as a marketing strategy of their products. Therefore, the hypothesis that states that there is no significant effect of the use of Facebook on the financial performance of small and medium size enterprises in Mezam Division (NWR), Cameroon was rejected.

Thus, this finding ties with previous studies such as the study of Momani (2016) who investigated on the effect of social media on small business performance in Jordan with the aims to identify the impact of social network on the financial and nonfinancial performance of small business firms. The study focused on the most important social networking sites used in Jordan, namely, Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, in order to find out the extent of their impact on the small-business firms performance regarding financial and non-financial aspects. The study showed a significant effect of social media on the performance of small business firms, where Facebook had the greatest impact on the financial performance of these firms, followed by Instagram, and in the last rank came Twitter, whereas Instagram came in the first place regarding the impact on the non-financial performance of these firms, in the second rank came Twitter and in the last rank came Facebook. This highlighted the significant role of social networking sites in influencing the financial performance of small business firms in Jordan in terms of the increase in sales volume, profit and the expansion of market share as well as the impact of this on non-financial performance of these firms in terms of gaining a greater number of clients, maintaining them, and gaining their trust in organization performance.

Also, according Mangold and Faulds (2009) social media marketing such as Facebook enables companies to achieve a better understanding and consideration of customer needs hence build effective relationships. From the definition of social media as an activities, practices and behaviors among communities of people who gather online to share information, knowledge and opinions through conversation, Facebook is seen as a developing platform that can be used by businesses towards interacting with customers. Through Facebook, small businesses can take the opportunity

of sharing information about the goods and services that they offer and targeted customers will get to see and comment about it.

Looking at hypothesis two of this study which states that there is no significant effect of the use of youtube on the financial performance of small and medium sized enterprises in mezam division (NWR) Cameroon. Statistically, findings showed that the use of YouTube has a very significant, positive and strong effect on the financial performance of SMEs ($P < 0.001$, $\text{far} < 0.05$). The positive sign of the correlation coefficient value ($R = 0.576^{**}$) implies that the financial performance of SMEs is more likely to increase when owners of SMEs adequately use YouTube as a marketing strategy of their products. Therefore, the hypothesis that states that there is no significant effect of YouTube on the financial performance of small and medium size enterprises in Mezam Division (NWR), Cameroon was rejected. Thus the finding can be related to that developed by kim & kom (2012), this theory state that social media marketing have proved to have a positive effect on the performance of an organization. The authors of the theory initially focused on the marketing activities used by luxury fashion brands to market their products. They included entertainment in the particular sector of the industry, customer interaction based on the goal of the business, trend, customization of the product and services offered to the target population for consumption and word of mouth. Their impact on firm performance was analysed in terms of brand equity, customer equity, purchase intention, value equity and equity linkage. This findings also ties with Smits & Mogos (2013). Investigated on the impact of social media on business performance. The purpose of this research was to explore the impact of social media and to analyze to what extent social media have impact on organizational capabilities and business performance. The researchers developed a research model and two simple propositions based on the resource based view of the firm. They analyzed the impact of six social media applications on six business capabilities and on business performance in SponsorPay, a start-up company since 2009 in the on-line game advertising industry. A mixed research methodology was deployed including qualitative analysis based on interviews and quantitative analysis based on a survey among 60 employees. Finding revealed that the use of social media enhances business capabilities and business performance.

According to hypothesis three of this study which states that there is no significant effect of the use Instagram on the financial performance of small and medium sized enterprises in mezam division (NWR) Cameroon. Findings showed that the use of Instagram has a very significant, positive and moderate effect on the financial performance of SMEs ($P < 0.001$, $\text{far} < 0.05$). The positive sign of the correlation coefficient value ($R = 0.204^{**}$) implies that the financial performance of SMEs is more likely to increase when owners of SMEs adequately use Instagram as a marketing strategy of their products. This finding ties with Neti (2011) opined that instagram has the best opportunity available to connect brand at a deeper level with a prospective consumers, hence a medium of socialization. Through instagram, different brands find themselves into a new word of a virtual customers and increase spread in marketing channels. Businesses and social media have become more sophisticated recently, with so many businesses using instagram to get certain type of customers with specific behavior, thereby significantly affecting SMEs financial performance. Also a quantitative research was conducted on the number of people who uses Instagram and for consumers if their buying decision is influenced with the use of Instagram. The sample counted 116 respondents and from the statistical perspective, the conclusions were established in terms of the univariate and bivariate analysis. Following the analysis of the research variables we can make a consumer profile that uses Instagram. Likewise, after doing the complex statistical analysis using SPSS and the analysis offered by the online platform the host of questionnaire, it can be seen how much it is influenced and the real impact of Instagram reflected in the behavior changes (Ioanas & Stoica, 2014).

Conclusion

From the research findings, some conclusions can be made about the study. The researcher concludes that the use of social media platforms such as facebook, youtube and instagram by

SMEs are positively related to SMEs financial performance. Though SMEs try to apply social media marketing on their business, there is still much to be done for improvement as they are still lacking in the technicality and functionality of these social media platforms which goes beyond just trying to post ones products on this platforms but implementing strategies that will attract and retain online customers as well as exploring other social media platforms for greater impact.

Also, from the findings the researcher could conclude that the location of the business, the duration of the business and the level of education of the employer or employee of the business which were found statistically significant had an overall effect on the financial performance of SMEs in mezzan division.

Viewing all what has been said and done in this part and especially backed by the results of the findings, the researcher can draw the conclusion that; SMEs in mezzan division (NWR) of Cameroon can achieve high and better level of financial performance through continuously updating, implementing or the amelioration of their social media strategies to fit and meet the needs of a wider population if it desires long term social media marketing sustainability.

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